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Product Development Based on Augmented Reality for Generation Z – A Case Study of the xSpot Startup

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ABSTRACT.....	3
Introduction.....	4
1. Augmented Reality in Marketing.....	5
1.1. Augmented Reality and Its Technological Aspects.....	5
1.2. The Augmented Reality Market.....	9
1.3. 5G Network and Augmented Reality.....	10
1.4. Case Studies.....	14
2. Generation Z – The Consumers of the Future.....	20
2.1. Characteristics of Generation Z.....	20
2.2. Comparison of Generation Z Against Other Consumer Types.....	23
3. Product Development from Concept to Validation in a Startup.....	27
3.1. Startup Characteristics.....	27
3.2. Design Thinking – Building and Clarifying the xSpot Idea.....	30
3.3. Business Model Canvas – Characteristics and Business Model of xSpot.....	40
3.4. Lean Startup Development – Characteristics and MVP Development of the xSpot Startup.....	47
4. Validation of the xSpot Product MVP.....	51
4.1. Research Problem.....	51
4.2. Variables and Indicators.....	53
4.4. Product Evaluation of xSpot.....	56
CONCLUSION.....	73
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	74
LIST OF FIGURES.....	79
LIST OF TABLES.....	80
APPENDIX LIST.....	81

ABSTRACT

The aim of this thesis was to identify a market gap that could be filled by a potential startup leveraging augmented reality (AR) technology, responding to the growing market demand for innovative and effective marketing channels that align with the preferences and behaviors of Generation Z consumers.

The first chapter presents augmented reality in the context of marketing. It thoroughly describes key aspects such as AR technology, the AR market, the impact of 5G networks on AR, and case studies where the use of AR led to marketing success. These cases show that when consumers actively engage with AR marketing campaigns, their involvement increases because interaction is initiated by the user. AR advertising achieves significantly better results than traditional channels, with conversion rates ranging from 20% to 80%.

The second chapter focuses on the target users of the potential startup, primarily Generation Z. This generation is first compared to others and then described in detail, highlighting traits such as their everyday presence in the digital world, and their use of mobile apps as primary tools for education and entertainment. They prefer apps that allow them to express uniqueness, creativity, and individuality, as well as marketing messages that are brief and straightforward.

The third chapter discusses the process of building a startup, from idea to MVP. It begins with an explanation of what a startup is and its core principles. It then presents tools such as design thinking, business model canvas, and lean startup development, followed by a practical section in which the outputs of these tools for the xSpot startup are developed, described, and visualized.

The fourth chapter is the empirical section, where a study was conducted with 116 respondents concerning AR and the xSpot startup concept. It includes sub-sections on research objectives, research problems, variables and indicators, methods, techniques, and tools. The study found that over 49% of respondents reacted positively to xSpot's value proposition. Additionally, the planned MVP functionality was validated, as it was based on creating an avatar and engaging in sports competition with other users. The largest group (38.8%) identified 'the ability to play as a self-created avatar' as the main feature missing in current AR apps lack most is "the ability to play as a self-created avatar," and 44% chose "playing tennis with a friend" as the most interesting AR experience. Moreover, 64% indicated they would visit a location to gain virtual benefits for their avatar, assuming the incentive was sufficiently attractive—showing strong support for xSpot's proposed model of interaction.

Introduction

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) are among the most innovative and modern technologies used in marketing communication and broadly understood entertainment. These technologies are likely to become the next key global revolution, completely changing how we perceive the world around us. Social changes are taking place in the global population, particularly the growing market importance of consumers born after 1995—Generation Z, the first generation raised with widespread access to the internet. Identifying the right channels to effectively reach this market segment is a key challenge for modern businesses, as traditional marketing channels prove ineffective.

Implementing innovative solutions that use the latest technologies in the context of marketing communication with the youngest consumers is crucial, as it can significantly enhance a brand's attractiveness in their eyes and directly translate into increased sales.

The main goal of this thesis is to identify a market gap that could be filled by a potential startup utilizing AR technology, responding to upcoming market demands for an innovative and effective marketing channel aligned with young consumers' preferences. The secondary goals of the thesis are to:

- characterize the consumer of the future,
- identify the best tools for defining the product scope,
- prepare the startup for investment.

This thesis adopts the following research hypotheses:

1. The use of AR technology in the xSpot startup has the potential to become a key tool in marketing communication with Generation Z.
2. Augmented Reality technology will enjoy increasing interest among members of Generation Z.
3. The AR market will see significant growth over the next decade.
4. The approach proposed in xSpot is positively received by Generation Z as an innovative, non-intrusive form of marketing communication.

These hypotheses will be analyzed and verified in the thesis, and this thesis draws conclusions based on the presented research.

1. Augmented Reality in Marketing

1.1. Augmented Reality and Its Technological Aspects

Augmented reality (AR) is a technology that enhances the physical world by adding a layer of digital information to it. Unlike virtual reality (VR), which creates a completely artificial environment, augmented reality appears directly over the view of the real world, enriching it with digital effects such as sound, animations, or graphics. The physical environment combined with computer-generated effects that change the perception of reality is what defines AR (Kovach, 2018). Another definition of AR is that it is a direct or indirect, real-time view of the physical environment enriched with virtual information generated by a computer. This technology combines interactive digital content with static real-world objects; it combines real objects with virtual ones (Carmigniani, 2010).

The concept of augmented reality dates back to the 1990s. The first commercial implementations were applied in the military and television. With the development of smartphones and the Internet, AR technology has gained new life and today is strongly associated with interactivity. 3D models are projected onto real objects or integrated with them in real time. Many applications using augmented reality now affect our social lives, habits, and the entertainment industry (Kovach, 2018).

Typically, AR applications combine digital animation with a special “marker” or use the GPS of a smartphone to initiate digital effects in a selected location. The augmentation occurs in real-time and in the context of a specific environment—for example, by displaying scoreboards in sports broadcasts (Kovach, 2018). The history and evolution of AR technology are as follows:

- **1950s** – Morton Heilig, a cinematographer, envisioned cinema that engages all the senses and creates the illusion of reality. In 1955, he wrote about it in an article titled Cinema of the Future. In 1962, he built the Sensorama machine (Carmigniani, 2010).
- **1960s** – Ivan Sutherland, with the help of Bob Sproull, developed the first head-mounted display (HMD) system that displayed primitive wireframe graphics. The device was called the “Sword of Damocles” due to its appearance.
- **1970s** – Myron Krueger created the Videoplace system, which allowed interaction with virtual objects using body movements.
- **1980s** – Steve Mann invented a wearable computer called EyeTap, which recorded the environment and displayed it with modifications. Douglas George and Robert Morris

created a system with a head-mounted display that showed astronomical data over the real sky.

- **1990s** – The term “augmented reality” was introduced by Thomas Caudell and David Mizell, who developed AR systems at Boeing for wiring aircraft. Louis Rosenberg created Virtual Fixtures at the U.S. Air Force Research Laboratory. In 1999, a team led by Frank Delgado and Mike Abernathy conducted the first tests of an AR navigation system that overlaid runway and street data on a video feed from a helicopter.
- **2000s** – Hirokazu Kato developed ARToolKit, a tool for overlaying graphics on live video. Trimble Navigation introduced an AR system in a helmet. In 2008, the Wikitude application was launched on Android – an augmented reality travel guide.
- **2010s** – In 2013, Google began testing Google Glass – glasses displaying digital information in real time. In 2015, Microsoft introduced HoloLens and Windows Holographic. In 2016, Niantic released Pokémon Go – an AR game that made \$2 million in its first week (Kovach, 2018).

With the help of augmented reality, various types of information such as 3D models, images, animations, and videos can be added to the real world. Users perceive these virtual objects in both natural and artificial lighting. Unlike virtual reality, AR allows the user to remain in their current environment and maintain awareness of their surroundings (Kovach, 2018).

Augmented reality can be displayed on various devices such as screens, glasses, portable devices, mobile phones, and head-mounted displays. This technology is closely related to systems such as S.L.A.M. (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping), which involves real-time location tracking and mapping, as well as depth tracking. It works by collecting data from sensors that calculate the distance to objects. Below are the most important components:

- **Cameras and sensors** – responsible for collecting data on user interactions and sending it for processing. Cameras on devices scan the surroundings, and based on this information, the device locates physical objects and generates 3D models. These may include specialized cameras like those in Microsoft HoloLens, or standard smartphone cameras used for photography and video recording..
- **Processing** – AR devices should ultimately function like small computers, as is the case with modern smartphones. This is because they require access to resources such as a processor, graphics processor, flash memory, RAM, Bluetooth, WiFi, and GPS in order to measure speed, angle, direction, and spatial orientation.

- **Projection** – The AR projector can be either glasses or a smartphone, which transfers data from the sensors and displays the digital content (the processing output) onto a viewing surface (Kovach, 2018).

Marker-based Augmented Reality (AR) – to overlay virtual elements onto the real world, a unique visual object, called a marker, must be scanned. This can be anything from a printed QR code to special symbols. When an AR device points its camera at the marker, it calculates the marker's position and orientation to correctly place the digital content. In this way, the marker triggers digital animations that users can view on their screens.

Figure 1. Marker-based AR

Source: (Kovach, 2018)

Markerless Augmented Reality (AR) – with the emergence of advanced camera systems and more precise sensors in mainstream devices, such as Apple's iPhone, augmented reality has transitioned from marker- or QR-code-based projections to markerless ones. Originally referred to as "dead reckoning," markerless AR uses a combination of dedicated camera systems, sensors, and complex math to accurately detect and map the real environment—for example, the location of walls and intersections. With the mapped space, the AR-enabled application can place virtual objects in the real-world context and keep them anchored without needing a QR code or image (Ridden, 2014).

Figure 2. Markerless AR

Source: (Ridden, 2014)

Location-based Augmented Reality (AR) – also known as position-based AR, uses GPS, a compass, gyroscope, and accelerometer to deliver data based on the user’s location. This data then determines what AR content can be found or accessed in a given area (Kovach, 2018).

Figure 3. Location-based Augmented Reality

Source: (Paladini, 2018)

1.2. The Augmented Reality Market

The rise of the VR/AR 1.0 market began when Facebook acquired Oculus in 2014. This was a clear signal to the world that these technologies would become key players in the coming years. That impulse inspired a generation of entrepreneurs, corporations, and venture capitalists to create the early VR/AR market. Despite significant technological progress and the gradual spread of new technologies, a mass VR/AR market has not yet fully emerged. It remains an emerging branch of the global economy, but one that carries with it innovation and immense potential.

According to Digi-Capital, the share of augmented reality technology in the immersive tech sector will significantly increase in less than a decade. When analyzing the market, one can identify many factors driving AR forward—such as new content, applications, and developments in gaming and entertainment sectors.

Mobile AR saw 2% higher revenues than forecasted for 2018, exceeding \$3 billion globally. The main sources included revenue from the App Store (primarily Pokémon Go), advertising spend (e.g., AR features in social media apps), and e-commerce sales (e.g., Houzz, which recorded an 11-fold increase in sales). The base of AR devices (i.e., configured devices) grew more slowly than expected, reaching over 850 million worldwide—but these are not all active users, meaning the actual number is significantly smaller. According to Digi-Capital's forecasts from the previous year (2018), there was no major growth in mobile AR applications. Developers are still trying to determine what works and what doesn't when it comes to mobile augmented reality.

The mobile AR market—meaning smartphones and AR glasses—could reach 2.5 billion devices and see revenue growth from \$70 billion to \$75 billion by 2023 (Digi-Capital, 2019). In reality, the number of AR users has increased in recent years. In 2017, only 37.6% of Americans used this technology. In 2019, that number rose to 68.7% of the U.S. population and is continuing to grow.

Figure 4. Number of Augmented Reality Users in the U.S.

Source: (Statista, 2019)

AR technology has become so widespread that 46% of Americans have likely used an AR application without even realizing it. For example, people using unusual filters on Facebook or Snapchat when taking selfies have experienced AR firsthand, even without knowing it.

Snapchat was one of the first mobile applications to popularize AR through filters. Shortly after Snapchat's launch, the mobile game Pokémon Go appeared. The game allows players to catch and train their own Pokémon at various locations throughout a city.

In addition to the applications mentioned above, there are also retail companies such as IKEA that use AR to help customers visualize furniture in their homes before making a purchase, thereby making the product selection process easier. Meanwhile, Mercedes uses an AI-powered chatbot in combination with AR. This allows customers to scan car parts with their smartphone camera, and the app automatically provides information about the specific component (Eira, A., 2020).

1.3. 5G Network and Augmented Reality

The 5G network brings enormous possibilities, best illustrated by a scenario in which millions of data points are transmitted from a single system to millions of connected devices around the world—instantaneously.

A powerful technology that stands on the verge of transforming all existing mobility and ushering in Economy 5.0 is wireless 5G networks.

Given the potential this technology carries, referring to it merely as a "network" would be highly dismissive. The 5G network will become the foundation of an entire ecosystem built on Internet-connected devices and will lead to a 180-degree shift in business and economic policies.

Figure 5. Global number of mobile devices supporting 5G from 2021 to 2025 (in billions)
Source: (Srivastav, 2020)

The paradigm shift that 5G may bring will have a lasting impact on many industries and open the door to innovation and transformation. The most immediate influence of high internet connectivity will be seen in the mobile app ecosystem.

5G technology offers several advantages over 4G, including:

- Faster fiber-equivalent speeds;
- Lower latency and fewer disruptions;
- Higher wireless capacity enabling more IoT device connections;
- Greater potential for seamless wireless connectivity;

Figure 6. The importance of 5G for mobile applications

Source: (Srivastav, 2020)

1. Faster Speed

The high download speed offered by 5G technology will allow users to download apps within seconds, regardless of the app's MB size. The key benefit here is the elimination of streaming delays and maintaining seamless data delivery.

2. Faster File Transfers

Faster transfers of files, money, or other electronically transferable data. A download speed of 490 Mbps and upload speeds of 100 Mbps create amazing opportunities in mobile app categories whose business models revolve around the movement of data or money from one account to another.

3. From Low to Zero Latency

There's nothing more frustrating for a smartphone user than an app that responds sluggishly. While latency is not a foreign concept to software engineering, 5G dramatically reduces user interaction delays to a point where responsiveness feels real-time. This aspect will be especially impactful for AR/VR-based apps, which require the transmission of large amounts of data.

According to IHS Economics, wireless 5G networks could generate up to \$12.3 trillion globally—across a broad range of industries. This figure is comparable to the total U.S. consumer spending in 2016. The economic transformation driven by 5G is expected to create

millions of jobs worldwide. Mobile app developers, in addition to content and infrastructure providers, are expected to be among the key professional groups to benefit from this evolution. Although no industry will be left untouched by the advantages brought by faster internet, some sectors will show signs of technological adoption and innovation faster than others.

1. Internet of Things (IoT)

Faster communication than ever before and long battery life—these two advantages of 5G wireless networks make ideal conditions for the development of the Internet of Things. According to a recent survey conducted by Gartner across various economic sectors, over 57% of respondents consider IoT the most promising niche. 5G technology will allow IT system developers to work in those IoT areas where the difference between 4 milliseconds and 40 milliseconds is critical.

The future lies in smart cities—creating intelligent infrastructure equipped with millions of real-time-operating sensors.

2. AR / VR

AR/VR is an emerging trend that will impact society at nearly every stage of life. Virtual elements will be visible on glasses, windows, screens—and primarily through smartphones. From attending a live event in Los Angeles while physically being in Poland, to accessing the historical background of every building or monument. AR/VR will finally enter the mainstream thanks to 5G. While the above examples focus mainly on entertainment, many other industries—healthcare, education, military—will benefit from a platform where reality and virtual environments are unified and inseparable.

Alongside the benefits of 5G, there are also challenges. The most important ones are listed below:

1. Security Concerns

As connection speeds increase, so too will the number of connected devices—meaning potential vulnerabilities in cybersecurity may arise.

2. Establishing 5G-Based Business Models

Faster network speeds will require new business models that fully leverage the technology's capabilities.

3. Multiple Versions of Applications

With the introduction of 5G, app audiences will be segmented. There will be users with 5G-capable devices, as well as those still using 2G or LTE-based devices (Srivastav, 2020).

1.4. Case Studies

The use of and interaction with AR is closely tied to user engagement, which is why consumers must be properly encouraged to engage with augmented reality to achieve its intended effect. However, once a user engages with AR, the marketing impact is more effective than in other forms of marketing communication. The immersion and interactivity of the experience or advertisement create an emotional connection with the user, which helps trigger positive brand associations more effectively. Consumer memory for marketing messages is 70% higher for augmented reality compared to other marketing channels. Through interaction, consumers connect with the brands they love in new, immersive ways thanks to AR.

Brands are already promoting themselves in this new digital space. One such example is Burger King. The Brazilian branch, noticing a decline in usage of their local mobile app, decided to creatively hijack a marketing campaign from their main competitor to promote their own menu. Using the Burger King app, users could point their smartphone cameras at a McDonald's ad and "burn" it, revealing a coupon for a free Whopper from Burger King. The campaign went viral on the internet and won a Cannes Lion award (Rogers, S. 2019).

Figure 7. "Burn That Ad" Augmented Reality Campaign by Burger King
Source: Rogers, S. 2019

Another brand that skillfully used AR technology is Gucci, the Italian fashion house. This is one of the best examples of how AR can help mobile shoppers make more informed decisions when purchasing products like shoes, cosmetics, and clothing. By allowing customers to see 3D visualizations of products, brands can better manage expectations and increase customer satisfaction. Satisfying the customer at the first stage of the purchase journey helps eliminate return handling costs from disappointed buyers and can potentially increase brand loyalty and future sales (Williams, R. 2019).

Figure 8. Gucci Mobile App Using Augmented Reality

Source: Williams, R. 2019

Through IKEA's AR smartphone app, users can browse various product categories and virtually place all kinds of furniture in their living room, bedroom, or outdoor space to see how it looks. Viewing items in one's own home helps customers determine whether they fit and look good (Mbryonic, 2019).

Figure 9. IKEA App in Augmented Reality

Source: Mbryonic, 2019

The agencies HappyLucky and 14Four created a promotional campaign for Adidas at four Finish Line store locations: Del Amo Fashion Center (LA), Park Meadows Mall (Denver), Water Tower Mall (Chicago), and Roosevelt Mall (New York). In the center of each store, a WebAR installation was set up containing hidden 3D content as part of the “Forever the Future” campaign. Shoppers could scan a QR code or enter a URL to activate the interactive layer. The AR experience began with the message: “Inspired by the past and excited for what’s next, this interactive space is designed to give you the best look at Adidas’ newest shoes. Tap to enter below and use your camera to unlock the modern AR space.” This example of ARCommerce is part of a growing trend of introducing interactive layers in physical retail stores to enhance traditional shopping experiences with digital content (8th Wall, 2019).

Figure 10. E-Commerce App in Augmented Reality as Part of Adidas Marketing Campaign

Source: 8th Wall, 2019

In cooperation with NBC Sports Philadelphia and the Blue agency, the Philadelphia Phillies live-streamed a WebAR activation as part of their latest marketing campaign featuring player Aaron Nola. During the NBC Sports Philadelphia news broadcast on August 16, 2019, a QR code appeared along with an image target in the outline of Aaron Nola. Viewers had the opportunity to activate the interaction in real time, hosting a 3D model of Aaron Nola in their living room and unlocking a \$10 discount on final game tickets. For those who missed the broadcast, the Phillies also posted the QR code on their website so everyone had a chance to take advantage of the offer.

Figure 11. Philadelphia Phillies Web App in Augmented Reality

Source: 8th Wall, 2019

As part of a series of WebAR experiences, a marketing campaign was also designed for a newly released LEGO set. The global campaign was conducted by the UK-based agency Hoopla Digital. Users could scan a QR code or visit a link to discover virtual ghosts that had escaped and were hiding in the toy store aisle. From a first-person perspective, users could help their LEGO friends, Jack and Parker, capture the ghosts.

Figure 12. LEGO Augmented Reality App

Source: 8th Wall, 2019

In 2019, General Mills launched a new cereal brand: Fillows, with Hershey's Cookies N' Creme and Pillsbury Cinnamon Roll fillings. Using interactive WebAR features, Fillows took cereal promotion to the next level by turning the packaging into interactive puzzles with multiple levels and interaction possibilities.

Figure 13. Web App in Augmented Reality by Philadelphia Phillies

Source: 8th Wall, 2019

The fact that AR advertising cannot be forcibly imposed on consumers ensures greater effectiveness and viewer engagement.

All the elements are in place to make AR ads a daily part of public life and provide businesses with a new form of communication that delivers better results than traditional promotional channels and formats. However, until a digital space emerges in society where users spend the majority of their time each day, marketers will not be able to push AR ads to the masses—only to a limited audience segment (Rogers, S. 2019).

2. Generation Z – The Consumers of the Future

2.1. Characteristics of Generation Z

Generation Z in Poland is highly diverse. Not every member of this generation feels that a friendly and open world is within reach. The greatest challenge facing Generation Z is that it is the most mentally, economically, and culturally divided generation among all post-WWII generational groups. It's important to note that this generation was raised after 1989, and it's most evident here who was given the opportunity by their parents for better education, global openness, or inherited wealth—and consequently, the chance for professional success. Typically, the parents of Gen Z individuals are today's 40-year-olds, who were able to take advantage of the opportunities brought by transformation and the free market in Poland. Gen Z not only “consumes” what their parents achieved but also feels their successes and failures. Experts believe that their behavior is influenced not just by education, but significantly by “home culture”—for example, whether books were read at home, whether they traveled, visited museums, and whether there was a supportive, development-friendly atmosphere (Pawłowska, 2013).

According to a report by Sparks & Honey (2014), in the United States, 26% of teens aged 16–19—members of Generation Z—participate in various types of volunteering. They are determined to make an impact on the world and genuinely believe they can do so. Because they are tech-savvy and have grown up immersed in technology, they adapt quickly to industries related to social media services, such as managing fan pages, designing websites, mobile games, animations, and in general, the IT and marketing sectors. In their careers, important factors include: salary, company prestige, and development opportunities. At the same time, many of them consider freelancing acceptable, challenging the notion that one must leave the house to work. “Going to work” is unthinkable to them when the same tasks can be done in their natural environment: smartphones, laptops, or tablets. For Generation Z, collaboration doesn't require being in the same room. A major advantage is their knowledge of foreign languages, allowing them to communicate with clients from around the world. The internet is their primary space for getting assignments. Gen Z is seen as the most consumption-oriented generation, exposed to more diverse marketing tactics than any previous generation—even Millennials. They're often described as "digital hippies," though at the same time, they subconsciously fall prey to advertising and trends. For this generation, everyone should be present not only on Facebook but

also on Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, and Snapchat. To Gen Z, social media participation isn't a passing trend—it's an essential part of daily life. Universities, employers, or favorite restaurants must have a presence there if they want to be seen as relevant (Jaworowicz, 2015).

Figure 14. Generation Z Online

Source: JWT Intelligence, 2012; Edudemic survey

Sociologists note that this generation is often seen as selfish and solitary. Born into times of general prosperity, many of them are only children—raised by parents who, due to work and lack of time, chose to have one child and compensated for their absence by spoiling them. The constant attention focused solely on them has led many Gen Z individuals to be egocentric, making it harder to form lasting bonds and relationships. Many are used to a comfortable lifestyle provided by their parents and take it for granted (Sparks & Honey, 2014).

Key traits of Generation Z consumers:

- **Images and video as the primary form of communication** – Gen Z embraces the TL;DR mindset (“Too Long; Didn’t Read”). Businesses recognize this and primarily communicate via memes, short videos, and images (Sparks & Honey, 2014).
- **Short attention spans** – The average attention span for advertisements dropped from 12 seconds in 2000 to just 8 seconds today. Gen Z consumes short bursts of information. Research shows their brains have evolved to process large amounts of information very quickly. Capturing and holding their attention is a challenge. They value time and want instant access to the latest smartphone info or problem solutions before they even recognize the issue exists (Sparks & Honey, 2014).

Figure 15. Decline in Generation Z's Presence on Facebook

Source: Sparks & Honey, 2013

Figures 14 and 15 show how in 2014, 25% of teens aged 13–17 left Facebook for Instagram, reflecting their privacy preferences—favoring platforms where photos and videos disappear after 24 hours (e.g., Instagram Stories or Snapchat). Research also shows that 17% of youth aged 8–16 use smartphones specifically to maintain privacy from parents. Snapchat, although underused in Poland, is very popular with Gen Z globally as it offers both creativity and anonymity. Thus, the best communication channels for short, engaging videos are Snapchat, Instagram, and YouTube (Sparks & Honey, 2014).

Figure 16. Growth in Generation Z's Presence on Instagram

Source: Sparks & Honey, 2013

Young people are addicted to social media but strive to protect their privacy. Research suggests that compared to Millennials, Gen Z is aware that emotional content can go viral—but also that it

might harm their careers in the long term. They understand that anything uploaded online stays there forever, so they tailor their content to each platform.

Gen Z typically does not own—and likely won't own—televisions. They consume information via mobile devices, and printed newspapers are seen as relics. Authenticity and content quality are paramount. Trust in vloggers, blogs, and the press is declining, partially due to the prevalence of product placement.

- **Unisex fashion as a central trend** – Individual style is more important than gender norms. Brands targeting Gen Z must communicate through hashtags, Stories, and emojis, using short, non-intrusive formats to engage this group (Sparks & Honey, 2014).
- **Creativity** – Gen Z seeks online fame and recognition as creative, ambitious, and fun. They value spaces for self-expression. The term YUCCIE (Young Urban Creatives) describes young people living in cities who keep up with the digital world, make films, design clothes, or even create custom skins for avatars. They want to stand out and be acknowledged as creative individuals. One way brands can win them over is by promoting their work—whether videos, package designs, or custom T-shirt lines (Wikipedia, 2020).

2.2. Comparison of Generation Z Against Other Consumer Types

Constantly changing market conditions under which customers make decisions (development of new technologies, increased access to information, supply of goods on the market, and the number of stimuli directed at recipients), as well as changes related to consumers themselves (new consumers marking their presence on the market and generational turnover), lead to the emergence of several consumer types (businessinsider, 2019). Social sciences suggest that for a group to be considered a generation, its members must be bound by a certain distinctive bond, shared beliefs, and values. Often, this internal glue is a common generational experience (e.g., the WTC attack or the declaration of martial law). Another factor that defines a generational boundary is the emergence of conflict between the "old" and the "young." Generational membership is primarily determined by birth year; thus, it is essentially a division between younger and older people. However, age is not the only factor—attitudes towards life, views, and beliefs also matter. Even within a single generation, people significantly differ not

only in age but also in values, perspectives, and life experiences. This reflects the need for businesses to adapt their market offerings to the evolving expectations and preferences of different consumer generations. Table 1 shows a typology of consumers and characteristic differences between them.

Table 1. Differences Between Consumer Generations

Features	Maturists (born before 1945)	Baby Boomers (1945–1960)	Generation X (1961–1980)	Generation Y (1981–1995)	Generation Z (after 1995)
Shaping events	WWII, Rock’n’Roll, fixed gender roles (especially for women), nuclear families	Cold War, “Swinging Sixties,” youth culture, post-war boom, Woodstock, rise of teenage influence, moon landing, family orientation	End of Cold War, Gorbachev/Reagan, fall of Berlin Wall, Thatcherism, first PCs, latchkey kids, early mobile tech	9/11 attacks, PlayStation, reality TV, social media, Iraq invasion, music festivals, Google Earth	Economic recession, global warming, energy crisis, globalization, mobile devices, Arab Spring, cloud computing, Wikileaks, user-generated content
Approach to technology	Irrelevant	Early adopters	Digital immigrants	Technologically independent	“Technoholics” – fully dependent on IT
Aspirations	Ownership	Job security	Work-life balance	Freedom and flexibility	Stability and security
Medium komunikacyjne	Formal letter	Phone	Email and SMS	SMS or social media	Handheld (or wearable) communication devices
Representative product	Car	TV	PC	Tablet or smartphone	Google Glasses, graphene, nanotech, 3D printing, self-driving cars
Financial decision preference	Face-to-face meeting	Prefers face-to-face but often opts for online	Online if possible, otherwise face-to-face	Face-to-face	Uses peer experiences to find the best solution
Communication preference	Direct (face-to-face)	Accepts direct, email, or phone	SMS or email	Online and mobile (text messages)	Face-to-face via mobile devices

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Generation X – consumers born in the second half of the 20th century. In the Polish context, this typically refers to those born between 1961 and 1983 and is sometimes called the "Nothing Seriously" or PRL generation. Often skeptical of the marketing-constructed world, they live without authorities and sometimes feel "skipped" by history, having experienced no major historical milestones during their youth (Wikipedia, 2020). This generation is characterized by dedication to work, often putting it first, even though they reject the so-called "rat race." They value "work-life balance" more than other generations, but the culture of work remains their defining trait (businessinsider, 2019). Generation X can be described as a society unsure of its direction, lost in the chaos of modern life shaped by fashion trends and ideals. The X symbol signifies the unknown. Belonging to this group is defined not by education or faith, but by a nonchalant lifestyle, lack of color, and sometimes consumerism or corporate affiliation (Rybcńska, 2016).

Generation Y – the Millennials. This group includes those born from 1984, sometimes up to 1997 in Poland (in the U.S., it includes the demographic boom of the 1980s and 90s). Also called the "Next Generation," "Millennium Generation," "Flip-Flop and iPod Generation," or simply the "Digital Generation" (Wikipedia, 2020). These consumers were raised during the free-market transformation and have no memory of communism or the Cold War in Eastern Europe (Polish Millennials do not remember the PRL era). Compared to Generation X, they are more up-to-date with tech trends and are active digital users. The internet is second nature—they are said to live in a "global village." Well-educated, they value life experience and quality of life over material possessions. Millennials tend to live with parents longer, delaying independence. They are confident, believe in their skills, dislike criticism, and have inflated expectations and a sense of uniqueness (businessinsider, 2019).

Generation Z, also known as Generation C (from the English "connect, communicate, change," referring to the Internet, communication, and readiness for change), is also referred to as the multitasking generation, the @ generation, or the silent generation. In Poland, this group includes people born after 1995 who are just entering the market, which is why their characteristics are still described with some caution. When attempting to describe Generation Z, one can present traits that will shape the behavior of these individuals across various markets in the future (Wikipedia, 2020).

This generation was mostly raised in prosperity, growing up in a world of new technologies, which makes it easy for them to adapt to an Internet-based reality. "Zers" navigate

the world of new technologies with ease and have no problem using the latest gadgets. Real-life and interpersonal interactions are often replaced with virtual ones. It can be said that Generation Z consists of young people who live in a virtual world, belonging to virtual communities formed by people with similar passions and interests. These are usually open individuals, often with several thousand Facebook friends—not only from Europe but also from around the world, such as China or the USA.

Remote work, operating complex machines, or using software programs is no obstacle for members of this generation. Their defining and most valuable trait is their familiarity with the virtual world. What matters most is knowing where to look for information or whom to ask, and they do this at lightning speed. This skill allows them to function smoothly, without limits or borders. Another defining trait is their ability to perform multiple tasks at once, which is why they are also called the multitasking generation. They can effortlessly follow several events at the same time, watch a movie, participate in multiple auctions, and chat with friends simultaneously. They quickly master new applications and communicate in foreign languages without hesitation. Their openness to the world means that what older generations see as a threat, they view with fascination. They enjoy traveling, are not afraid to meet new people, and are open to working or interning on “the other side of the world” (Hysa, 2016, pp. 389–390).

In summary, based on the above characteristics, the most important communication traits of Generation Z are catchy, short, and digital messages, preferably in graphic or video form. However, there is still plenty of room for innovative marketing communication forms based on new technologies. The potential of new communication channels is significant, as Generation Z quickly adapts to new applications that meet their needs. It is crucial, however, that both the channel and the message are not intrusive and that they engage young people in a way that allows them to express their uniqueness and creativity.

3. Product Development from Concept to Validation in a Startup

3.1. Startup Characteristics

A solid plan is an excellent foundation for sophisticated improvisation, while future success depends on the proper development of the present. Therefore, it is important to translate a concept for a business venture into a concrete and realistic technical-economic plan that takes the form of a mature project.

In the business life cycle, several phases can be distinguished, such as: seed stage, startup stage, expansion stage, and replacement stage (Flejterski S., 2007, p. 43). The first phase of a company's operations is extremely important, as this is when the decision to start the business takes place, the basic goals of its operation are specified, and the market assumptions for the business are established. During this period, actions are also taken to formalize the organizational and legal system of the company and to choose the methodology. These activities are particularly popular in businesses related to the IT industry. They are aimed at relatively quickly achieving results in the form of new innovative IT products and services, due to the relatively short time to capture initial outcomes—as well as and a high degree of uncertainty regarding the product's final form (Kolpak M., 2013).

The phase referred to as the startup or launch phase likely has the greatest strategic importance when it comes to subsequent stages of company growth and development. If poorly executed, it can result in business failures or, in critical situations, the collapse of the company in the long term (Lachiewicz S., Matejun M., 2011, pp. 61–84).

By definition, a startup is a new business entity that has relatively recently started operations and is still in its initial stage of development. It is usually a micro or small business in its first year of operation, not yet selling its products or services commercially but preparing its business offering and collecting the necessary marketing data related to market entry (PARP, 2011). A startup may also result from the division, expansion, specialization, or reorganization of an existing company (Eurostat, 2007).

The startup stage is a period of company development in which such aspects as securing capital, presenting ready products and services, and creating a strategy for market

introduction are essential. This is a period characterized by the search for a profitable business model, high investment risk, and operations under extreme uncertainty. As presented by P. Graham in Figure 17, it is a phase of dynamically changing conditions associated with market entry with an innovative service or product and is actively pursued until the freshness and novelty of the product no longer affect the market.

The initial slump, which is the first and most painful in the startup life cycle, often leads to startups ceasing any further activities and ultimately failing. Finding strength in the team during the first crisis and surviving it offers potential prospects for improvement. Moreover, additional financing and the ability to use gained experience and skills contribute to restoring financial liquidity and gradually increasing economic potential (Graham P., 2012).

Figure 17. Startup Curve

Source: Graham P. (2012)

The time a company goes through the above period is often associated with strategic dilemmas when it is necessary to define goals and the means of achieving them. However, in most newly formed companies in Poland, the strategy and business approach result from intuitive actions, a passive stance toward competitive strategy, and flexibility, rather than conscious decisions (Zelek A., Maniak G., 2013).

To minimize uncertainty and the risk of failure, the startup stage should be internally organized and carried out in steps as presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Startup Development Stages

Source: Stankiewicz M. (2013)

Following a predetermined plan of action allows avoiding potential errors such as (startup.di, 2011):

1. Basing ideas on identical benchmarks – just because a concept succeeded on the market before doesn't mean it will work again or fit your business model, so avoid replicating previously implemented projects.
2. Lack of defined project assumptions – for a project to succeed, it must have a strong foundation in the form of a well-defined target group, market analysis (competition), and a financing model.
3. Lack of a well-developed business model, which is key to the financial success of the project.
4. Absence of a team or a trustworthy project contractor (with experience in delivering similar products).
5. Lack of trust in the selected contractor.
6. Insufficient financial resources or no allocated marketing budget.
7. Not measuring the effectiveness of actions taken – a management issue where there is no documentation or monitoring of which channels most effectively bring in new customers and sales.
8. Failure to account for potential additional costs that may arise during project execution.
9. A product that is too complex and overbuilt at launch – young companies try to deliver a polished product instead of focusing on the core functionalities that are key for users and validating them on the market as quickly as possible.

10. Unrealistic project time commitments – underestimating time estimates and assigning them to deadlines for delivering parts of the project.
11. No financial cushion for the first few or several months of operation, which may yield little or no income.

It is important to remember the sequence of actions taken and the key issues related to project implementation, primarily securing a stable source of funding. Then, the business idea should be verified, and all available tools should be used to assess the risk of failure.

3.2. Design Thinking – Building and Clarifying the xSpot Idea

Design thinking is an iterative process in which we aim to understand the future user of the created product, challenge design assumptions, redefine problems, and try to identify alternative strategies and solutions. At the same time, it provides techniques based on a proactive approach to problem-solving, which in practice means a way of thinking, working, and a set of practical methods (Simon H., 1968).

Many variants of this process are used, ranging from three to even seven phases, stages, or modes. However, they are all very similar. Generally, this method can be defined as a way of working in which multidisciplinary teams are able to create innovations that combine elements of design, engineering, business, and social sciences. This tool allows for the creation of innovative services or products, optimizations in customer service, or the development of new communication standards with clients (Serafiński B., 2009, p. 40).

The methodology is also referred to as a process focused on the human being and their needs. It can be used to create a new product, service, or to meet business challenges and problems (Lockwood T., 2009).

Another definition describes design thinking as a discipline that uses designers' methods and practical judgment to meet the needs of a specific group of people through a technologically feasible solution and one that a prudent business strategy can turn into value for the end customer and a market opportunity (Brown T., 2008, p. 86).

In Polish literature, design thinking is defined as "project-based thinking," described as a concept that uses the sensitivity of the designer and their working methods. It combines people's desires and needs with technological possibilities, which in turn creates a strategy

that delivers the most essential values to the consumer and creates market opportunities (Gawroński H., 2012, p. 15).

All variants of design thinking share the same principles. Below is the five-phase model proposed by the Hasso-Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford, also known as D.school. This concept is a leader in the practical application and teaching of design thinking. The five phases of this concept are as follows:

1. **Empathize** – This initial stage of the process involves learning as much as possible about the final users for whom the product is being designed. One way to do this is through interviews and observation. The aim is to answer questions like: Who exactly is my user, and what matters most to them? Creators believe everything starts with empathy, allowing a deep understanding of users' needs. The key is identifying and defining so-called "hidden motivations" influencing human behavior, and understanding the technological or market constraints of the project. Methods used include interviews, surveys, observations, empathy maps, and environment analysis. Special attention should be paid to user behavior observation, as users may create and use amateur improvements that can significantly contribute to the product design (Helman J., Rosienkiewicz M., 2019).
2. **Define** – In this phase, a point of view is created based on user needs and insights, allowing the team to answer: What are the customers' needs? Information gathered earlier is synthesized to identify and articulate the core problem. Designers must reject habitual thinking and limited mental frameworks to view the problem from a broader or different perspective. Properly defining the problem makes it easier to chart a path toward effective solutions. Techniques include the "5 Whys" method and mapping the problem on a how-why axis (Helman J., Rosienkiewicz M., 2019).
3. **Ideate** - This phase involves brainstorming and generating as many ideas as possible for potential solutions to the previously defined problem. There are no bad ideas—every idea, even the wildest one, is worth consideration. Beyond knowledge, creativity, inventiveness, and boldness are required. Team members must refrain from judging or criticizing others' ideas. The solution is chosen democratically, and a prototype is built around it. Tools include brainstorming and the "six thinking hats" method (Helman J., Rosienkiewicz M., 2019).
4. **Prototype** - In this phase, a prototype of one or more ideas is built to illustrate and demonstrate them to the rest of the team. This answers the question: How can I sell my

idea? A prototype is only a preliminary sketch of the product, physically representing a problem-solving solution. Its goal is not to build a complex or final product but to help visualize the solution and collect user feedback. This helps determine whether the product fits the market or needs a complete redesign. Early-stage prototypes help identify errors quickly and inexpensively. Constant improvement and user evaluation reduce the risk of final failure (Helman J., Rosienkiewicz M., 2019).

- 5. Test** - This stage involves showing the prototype to the end user to get feedback. This interaction helps answer: What worked and what didn't? The solution is validated in the real environment it is intended for. Appropriate parameters and values should be established to present clear test results (Helman J., Rosienkiewicz M., 2019).

These five phases are not always sequential. They don't follow a specific order and often occur in parallel or repeat iteratively. They should not be viewed as a hierarchy or step-by-step process, but as a set of modes contributing to an innovative project (Dam F.R., Siang T.Y., 2020).

Sometimes the easiest way to understand an intangible concept like design thinking is to understand what it is not. People naturally develop thinking patterns based on repetitive actions and commonly available knowledge. These patterns help apply known solutions to familiar situations, but can also block access to new ways of seeing or solving problems. These mental patterns, or "schemas," are triggered when we encounter environmental stimuli. A schema for "dog" may include four legs, fur, sharp teeth, a tail, paws, etc. Even weak or partial stimuli may trigger the full schema—like fleeing from a threatening dog. Since these schemas are triggered automatically, they can prevent us from properly interpreting a situation or identifying a problem in a new way (Dam F.R., Siang T.Y., 2020).

Out-of-the-box thinking can provide innovative solutions but is challenging because people rely on familiar mental patterns. A well-known anecdote illustrates this: A truck got stuck under a low bridge, and experts debated solutions—dismantling the truck or the bridge. A boy passing by suggested, "Why not let the air out of the tires?"—and the truck drove free. This story symbolizes how obvious solutions are often overlooked due to self-imposed limitations. Experts, in particular, depend on established patterns. Design thinking promotes questioning assumptions and seeking new approaches (Dam F.R., Siang T.Y., 2020).

Design thinking is referred to as "thinking outside the box" because designers aim to develop novel approaches beyond standard methods. It focuses on improving products through user

interaction analysis and environmental study. It also emphasizes asking difficult questions and testing assumptions to confirm or reject them. After analyzing problem conditions, idea generation should reflect real constraints. Design thinking supports deep problem exploration and conducting appropriate research, prototyping, and testing to explore product or service improvements. Final solution selection is based on rational choice and further testing to ensure the best outcome (Dam F.R., Siang T.Y., 2020).

Figure 19. Design Thinking Process

Source: (Dam F.R., Siang T.Y., 2020)

Tools and Techniques Used in the Design Thinking Method

The tools used by designers to communicate with business partners and solve their problems come directly from the fields of design and engineering. The project-based approach, i.e., multidisciplinary thinking, has adopted tools and methods from various fields of knowledge, including engineering, art, psychology, and anthropology (Tschimmel K., 2012, p. 11). Below are selected techniques used during the process of designing unconventional and innovative solutions.

Empathy Map

To carry out a good project, one must thoroughly understand the people for whom the solution is being developed. The empathy map helps analyze observations and facilitates the discovery of unexpected insights. This tool is used during the empathizing phase and enables standardized analysis of consumer needs. The map consists of four fundamental

elements, each representing a different trait necessary to define customer desires (D.school, 2013).

Figure 20. Empathy Map

Source: (D.school, 2013)

- **What does the user feel and think?** The purpose of this first part of the analysis is to assess the consumer's attitude toward the identified problem. The focus should not only be on their opinions about services and products, but also on what is genuinely important to them (even if it is not explicitly stated). Consider elements like aspirations, dreams, and fears. It is also crucial to identify what the user wants to achieve and what they would prefer to avoid (D.school, 2013).
- **What does the user hear?** This section focuses on what the client hears—both positive and negative—about the problem from people such as friends, family, or colleagues. One should also assess who has the greatest influence on the user and through what means that influence is exerted (D.school, 2013).
- **What does the user see?** This element involves describing what the client sees around the problem. A detailed characterization of their environment, market, or other relevant situations should be conducted. Pay special attention to key people in the user's surroundings and the issues they face (which may be similar to the analyzed problem). This is also the time to analyze the competition's offerings (D.school, 2013).

- **What does the client say and do?** The final stage analyzes the subject's behavior in routine and everyday situations, including social ones. It examines attitudes toward family, friends, or acquaintances in various circumstances. Consider how the client behaves in social settings, whether they influence others, and whether there is a difference between what the user thinks and what they say.

All the above segments complement one another, giving the analyst a complete picture of the empathy of the studied individual or group. This enables the definition of two additional key aspects:

- **Gains (Joys)** – These are everyday situations that bring the client positive emotions. The analysis should highlight all motivating factors and assess their importance in achieving success.
- **Pains** – This refers to what the client fears. Feelings such as anxiety or fear should be identified, along with the concerns troubling the user. Potential problems that need to be overcome to reach the set goal must be defined. Additionally, risk factors that should be eliminated must be identified (D.school, 2013).

The 5 Why Method – “5 Times Why”

The 5 Why technique, which literally translates as “5 times why,” is an iterative method used to analyze cause-and-effect relationships for a selected problem (Ohno T., 1988). The fundamental goal of this technique is to identify the root cause of a problem by repeatedly asking the question “why?”, where each answer forms the basis for the next question. The number “5” in the name comes from the empirical observation that five iterations are usually sufficient to resolve the issue. Questions should continue until the root cause is discovered and addressed.

Figure 21. Example Application of the 5 Why Method

Source: (Ohno T., 1988)

It is important to note that at the very bottom of the ladder, the answer should point to a process. This is the most critical element in the “5 Why” method—the real cause of the problem should be traced back to a process that may not be functioning properly or may not exist at all. The most common mistake is to respond with “classic answers” such as financial constraints, lack of human resources, or insufficient time. While these may reflect real challenges, they are often beyond direct human control. Therefore, when applying this technique, the focus should be on understanding why the process is failing.

The 6 Thinking Hats Method

When generating new ideas, the 6 Thinking Hats method, also known as the DeBono technique, can be very useful. This method is based on discussing different ideas while looking at them from various perspectives (DeBono E., 1999). The six metaphorical hats represent different states of mind—when we “put on” a particular hat, symbolizing a mental state, we view everything differently (Ohno T., 1988).

The hats are as follows:

- **Red Hat – expresses emotions** – What feelings arise when discussing the idea?
- **White Hat – expresses objectivity** – What knowledge do we have regarding the specific idea?
- **Black Hat – expresses pessimism** – What doesn't work about the idea?

- **Yellow Hat – expresses optimism** – What is likely to succeed?
- **Green Hat – expresses possibilities** – What could potentially develop from this idea?
- **Blue Hat – expresses organization** – Organizes the session and guides the overall approach.

The 6 Thinking Hats technique uses a model of parallel thinking, aiming to collect as many perspectives as possible on a given topic. It enables the evaluation of proposed solutions in a structured and organized way. During an idea generation session, all participants wear the same "hat color," beginning with the blue one (D.school, 2013).

Table 2. Guiding Questions in the 6 Thinking Hats Method

Hat Color	Representation	Guiding Questions
White Hat	Objectivity	What facts do you know?
Red Hat	Emotions	How do you feel about this topic? How do you react to it? What specific emotions do you feel?
Yellow Hat	Optimism	Why do you think it's worth doing? What positive aspects do you see? What are the strengths of this idea?
Black Hat	Pessimism	Do you think this will work? What are the weaknesses? What negative aspects do you notice?
Green Hat	Possibilities	What should be changed to make it different? How can this be done more effectively? What else could be done?
Blue Hat	Organization	What has been accomplished so far? What mindset is required? What should happen next?

Source: Based on D.school, 2013

Focusing the entire team on one mindset (hat color) at a time allows for better group collaboration compared to each person having a different hat. This way, teammates understand and align their thinking at a given moment, fostering mutual understanding.

In summary, this methodology allows for generating creative ideas and solutions through a holistic understanding of people. With a solid foundation in science and rationality, design thinking aims to develop a comprehensive and empathetic understanding of the problems users face. Particular attention is paid to empathizing with target customers. This includes abstract or subjective concepts, such as emotions, needs, motivations, and factors

influencing behavior. The entire process is more sensitive to the context in which users operate, as well as the problems and obstacles they may encounter while interacting with a product (Dam F.R, Siang T.Y, 2020).

Startup Concept: xSpot (based on the design thinking method):

- **Problem**

- Lack of an interactive mobile AR game – The market currently offers static uses of augmented reality, but lacks an interactive multiplayer AR game that can fully utilize the potential of the technology.
- Lack of a standardized environment for embedding innovative AR ads – Companies (e.g., restaurants) that want to attract young customers through innovative marketing do not have a platform enabling them to do so.

- **Solution**

- AR Advertising Environment – Providing businesses with a space to place AR ads at their physical locations, along with delivering a target audience that these ads are meant to attract.
- AR Game – Offering a mobile game in which players can create and develop their character in augmented reality, both locally and in various locations.
- Connecting Real and Virtual Worlds – Combining real-world locations with virtual benefits by rewarding players who check in at specific places in the real world.

- **Prototype**

- For Smartphone Users – Mobile AR Game – After downloading the game, players will create and be responsible for developing their character. This includes constant training and improvement in order to become better in multiplayer battles and climb global rankings. A player can train their character even in their own room, but to battle another player, both must be in the same physical location. Additionally, players can gain extra points by visiting “Spots” in real life, gaining an advantage over those who only develop their character in one location.

- For Businesses – Environment for Embedding AR Ads on the Game Map (available in App Store and Google Play) – By pinning their location on the map and purchasing a feature (e.g., strength points for player avatars or unique mini-games for added entertainment), restaurants and other businesses can attract new customers and communicate with them through a new marketing channel—an AR mobile game.

3.3. Business Model Canvas – Characteristics and Business Model of xSpot

Creating a Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a tool that streamlines managing an idea and guides it toward success, understood as the value derived from the concept. The most important aspect when preparing a proper business model is to recognize what lies behind the name and to make the designer aware of the project's resources, strengths, and the benefits stemming from the value offered to customers (Osterwalder A., Pigneur Y., 2010).

A business model is a company's plan that describes how it intends to make money, focusing on aspects such as: who the target customer base is, how value is delivered to them, and how it is financially structured. The Business Model Canvas allows these components to be defined on a single page. It is a strategic management tool that enables visualization and evaluation of a business idea or concept. This one-page document contains nine blocks representing the core elements of a business. It surpasses the traditional business plan, which spans several pages, by offering a much simpler way to understand the diverse components of a company that make it function as a whole. The right side of the model focuses on the customer or market (external factors beyond the company's control), while the left side focuses on the business (internal factors largely under the company's control). In the center are the value propositions, representing the exchange between the company and its customers (Athuraliya A., 2019).

This model is the best way to visualize a business concept because:

1. It provides a quick overview of the business model and excludes unnecessary details compared to a traditional business plan.
2. Its visual nature makes it easier to understand and reference individual sections.

3. It is simple to edit and present to stakeholders.
4. It shows how various aspects of the business are interconnected.
5. It can be used by both large corporations and startups.
6. It is easily used for brainstorming around an effective business model.

Figure 22. Business Model Canvas

Source: (Creately, 2019)

Creating a business model using this method should begin with explaining each of its components. The canvas includes nine building blocks: value propositions, customer segments, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key partners, key activities, and cost structure.

Below is a detailed description of each component:

- **Customer Segments**

These are groups of individuals or companies the business wants to reach and sell its product or service to. Segmenting customers based on similarities—such as geographic area, gender, age, behaviors, interests, etc.—allows the company to better meet their needs, particularly by tailoring the solutions provided. After a thorough analysis of customer segments, the company should identify the most attractive audience and create a persona model to facilitate its identification (Osterwalder A., Pigneur Y., 2010).

Figure 23. Target Audience Model

Source: Creately, 2019

There are various customer segments that a business model can be targeted toward:

- **Mass Market:** A business model focused on mass markets does not divide customers into segments. Instead, it targets the general population or a large group of people with similar needs. An example of such a product is a telephone.
 - **Niche Market:** This model focuses on a specific group of people with unique needs and characteristics. In this case, value propositions, distribution channels, and customer relationships should be tailored to their specific requirements. An example would be buyers of sports shoes.
 - **Segmented:** Based on slightly different needs, various groups can be identified within the main customer segment. This approach allows for the creation of different value propositions, distribution channels, etc., to meet the needs of those segments.
 - **Diversified:** This segment includes customers with very different needs.
 - **Multi-sided Markets:** This includes interdependent customer segments. For example, a credit card company serves both cardholders and merchants who accept those cards (Athuraliya A, 2019).
- **Customer Relationships**

In this section, the company must define the type of relationship it will maintain with each customer segment or how it will interact with them during the purchasing process. Types of customer relationships include:

- **Personal assistance:** Contact with the customer via email or phone.
- **Dedicated personal assistance:** A dedicated representative is assigned to the customer.
- **Self-service:** No close relationship is maintained, but all necessary help is provided for the customer to manage on their own.
- **Automated services:** An automated process or machine helps customers carry out services independently.
- **Communities:** An online community is created where customers can help each other solve problems related to the product or service.
- **Co-creation:** The company allows the customer to be involved in designing or developing the product.

- **Communication Channels**

This block aims to describe how the company will communicate and reach customers. Channels are touchpoints that connect the market with the business. They play a key role in raising awareness about the product or service and conveying the company's value proposition. There are two types of channels:

- **Owned channels:** Website, social media, internal sales.
- **Partner channels:** Partner websites, wholesale distribution, retail sales.

- **Revenue Streams**

Revenue streams are the sources from which the company earns money by selling its products or services to customers. This block should describe how revenue is generated from the proposed value proposition. A revenue stream can belong to one of the following revenue models:

- **Transaction revenues:** From customers who make a one-time payment.
- **Recurring revenues:** From ongoing payments for continuous services or after-sales services.

There are also several ways to generate revenue:

- **Asset sales:** Selling ownership rights of a product to the buyer.
- **Usage fees:** Charging customers for using a product or service.
- **Subscription fees:** Charging customers for regular and consistent access to a product.

- **Lending / Leasing / Renting:** Customers pay to gain exclusive rights to use an asset for a specific time.
- **Licensing:** Customers pay for permission to use the company's intellectual property.
- **Brokerage fees:** Revenue from acting as an intermediary between two or more parties.
- **Advertising:** Charging for advertising a product, service, or brand through the company's platform.

- **Key Activities**

In this section, the question to be answered is: What activities/tasks need to be performed to achieve the business goal? They must focus on delivering the value proposition, reaching customer segments, maintaining customer relationships, and generating revenue. There are three categories of key activities:

- **Production:** Designing, manufacturing, and delivering a product in large quantities and/or at the highest quality.
- **Problem-solving:** Finding new solutions to individual customer problems.
- **Platform/Network:** Creating and maintaining platforms.

- **Key Resources**

This section lists the key resources or main inputs needed to carry out key activities and deliver the value proposition. Types of key resources include:

- **Human:** Employees
- **Financial:** Cash, credit lines, etc.
- **Intellectual:** Brand, patents, intellectual property, copyrights
- **Physical:** Equipment, inventory, buildings

- **Key Partners**

Key partners are external companies or suppliers that will help you carry out key activities. These partnerships aim to reduce risk and acquire resources. Types of partnerships include:

- **Strategic alliances:** Partnerships between non-competitors
- **Cooperation:** Strategic partnership between competitors
- **Joint ventures:** Partners developing a new business together
- **Buyer-supplier relationships:** Ensures reliable supplies

- **Cost Structure**

This block identifies all costs associated with operating the given business model. It should focus on evaluating the costs of creating and delivering the value proposition, generating revenue streams, and maintaining customer relationships. This becomes easier after defining key resources, activities, and partners. Companies may be, cost-driven: focused on minimizing costs wherever possible or value-driven, focused on maximizing value for the customer (Athuraliya A, 2019).

- **Value Propositions**

This is the fundamental building block of the business model and represents the unique solution (product or service) to a customer segment's problem or creates value for that segment. A value proposition should be unique or differ from the competition's offer. If it's a new product, it should be innovative and groundbreaking; if it's an existing product, it should stand out with new features and attributes. Value propositions can be: quantitative: Price and speed of service, qualitative: Customer experience or design (Pucher J., 2012)

To summarize, the BMC (Business Model Canvas) is a business model startup template used to visualize a business's concept and key elements. It provides a holistic view of the business with answers to key questions about the company or product's value, infrastructure, customers, and finances.

Below is the model created specifically for the xSpot startup, presenting the most important features of the concept. In my opinion, the key elements are:

- **Unique value proposition:** We allow restaurants to attract new customers in a way never seen before. Through a mobile game in which players continuously develop their characters to win battles with friends in augmented reality.
- **Proposed pricing model for restaurant location listings:**
 - Spot (1 month) – 60.00 PLN
 - Spot (3 months) – 150.00 PLN
 - Spot (6 months) – 250.00 PLN
 - Spot (12 months) – 450.00 PLN

These two elements reflect the core value proposition for smartphone users. The mobile game will be more engaging than all others thanks to an advanced character development system based on visited locations and completed tasks. On the other hand, restaurants (the chosen business type for the MVP, later to include clothing stores, hair salons, etc.) benefit from new, gamified advertising opportunities.

Table 3. Business Model Canvas for xSpot Startup

<p>8. Problem</p> <p>The market currently demonstrates a static use of augmented reality, while there is a lack of an interactive multiplayer game that would utilize the full potential of this technology.</p> <p>Companies (e.g., restaurants) that would like to attract young customers through innovative marketing do not have the tools to do so, as there is currently no such solution available on the market.</p>	<p>1. Key Activities / Processes</p> <p>Developing a web application that serves as a SaaS system allowing restaurants to create their own Spots.</p> <p>Developing a mobile game designed to attract new users.</p> <p>Promoting the mobile app and actively selling and reaching out to new restaurants.</p>	<p>2. Unique Value Proposition</p> <p>We enable restaurants to attract new customers in an unprecedented way—through a mobile game in which players continuously develop their own characters in order to win duels with friends in augmented reality.</p>	<p>4. Customer Relationships</p> <p>A marketing team focused on communication and the development of both the web and mobile applications, working closely with players and active restaurants aiming to attract new customers.</p>	<p>1. Target Customer Segments</p> <p>Restaurants looking to attract new customers to their location in order to increase sales.</p> <p>Mobile gamers aged 13 to 35.</p>
	<p>6. Key Resources Required to Run the Business</p> <p>Intellectual: Knowledge of the segment, expectations, and characteristics of Generation Z.</p> <p>A team composed of specialists and enthusiasts.</p> <p>Financial resources for product development and promotion.</p>		<p>3. Channels to Reach Customers (Sales Channels)</p> <p>An active sales team targeting new restaurant clients.</p> <p>A marketing team focused on reaching new players through social media, YouTube influencers, and blogs.</p>	
<p>9. Cost Structure</p> <p>A project team focused on product development.</p> <p>Application promotion targeting mobile app users.</p> <p>Active sales of spots to restaurants aiming to increase sales.</p> <p>Maintenance of server infrastructure.</p>		<p>5. Revenue Streams</p> <p>Fees for placing a restaurant location on the map:</p> <p>Spot (1 month) – 60.00 PLN</p> <p>Spot (3 months) – 150.00 PLN</p> <p>Spot (6 months) – 250.00 PLN</p> <p>Spot (12 months) – 450.00 PLN</p>		

Source: Own elaboration

3.4. Lean Startup Development – Characteristics and MVP Development of the xSpot Startup

Economic development can be based on various premises; however, the most important factor is a suitable idea whose execution will yield positive results in a given location. Often, the impetus for interesting business ventures comes from natural conditions and the possibilities of utilizing them on the one hand, and from cultural specificity and the mentality of society on the other. Ultimately, this translates into the ability to transform an idea into a product by adapting it to the specific conditions of a dynamically changing market environment, while also proactively addressing the expectations of end users (Hildebrandt A., 2007).

The Lean Startup method is an approach to building and managing startups and delivering the desired product to end consumers more quickly. It emphasizes how to run a startup—when to "pivot" and take a new direction, and when to persevere and grow the company with maximum acceleration. Many startups begin with a product idea, convinced that there is a market demand for it. Then months or even years are spent perfecting the product—without ever showing it to potential customers, not even in its most basic form. If they fail to reach a broad customer base, it's likely because they never talked to potential consumers or determined whether the product was interesting to them (Ries E., 2011).

Figure 24. Lean Startup Development Diagram

Source: (Ries E., 2011)

Eliminate Uncertainty

The lack of a tailored management process has led many startups—or more precisely, “institutions designed to create a new product or service under conditions of extreme uncertainty”—to abandon the entire process. They adopt a “just do it” approach, which avoids any form of structured management. Using the Lean Startup approach, companies can create order instead of chaos by providing tools for continuously testing their vision (Ries E., 2011).

Work Smarter, Not Harder

The Lean Startup methodology assumes that every startup is an experiment trying to answer the questions: “Should this product be built?” and “Is it possible to build a sustainable business around this product or service?” This experiment is more than just a theoretical study—it is the first product. If it succeeds, it allows the manager to take further steps such as acquiring initial users, expanding the team, and ultimately starting to build the final product. The experiment ensures that before a product is ready for wide distribution, it already has defined customers, solves real problems, and provides a detailed specification of what should be built (Ries E., 2011).

Develop an MVP

The core element of the Lean Startup methodology is the feedback loop: build, measure, learn. The first step is to identify the problem to be solved and then develop a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) to begin the learning process as soon as possible. Once the MVP is defined, the startup can begin working on its improvement. This process requires proper measurement and learning—factors must answer the questions of cause and effect and must allow for actionable improvements to the product (Ries E., 2011).

Validated Learning

The measure of progress in manufacturing is the production of increasingly higher-quality goods. For startups, the unit of progress is validated learning—a rigorous method for demonstrating progress when operating in an environment of extreme uncertainty. It is essential to make and document progress. When a company focuses on finding the right product to build—that is, one that customers want and will pay for—it doesn’t need to spend months waiting to launch a beta version to pivot. Instead, it can adjust its plans gradually, one conversation at a time (Ries E., 2011).

Based on the above methodology known as Lean Startup, which serves to develop startup concepts and provides management guidance, a functional scope was created for the MVP of the xSpot product, presented in Table 4. This paper includes only the part strictly related to the mobile user—the player—who is the main driving force behind the entire business model. While creating the functional scope of the MVP, the main focus was on gameplay and engaging the player to return to the app frequently and stay in it as long as possible. Once the gameplay itself is validated and found attractive to users, the app can be expanded with additional modules and features. The rest of the functionalities developed for other system users such as the Global Admin (the person managing spots on behalf of xSpot) and Web Player (a restaurant employee or anyone who wants to create their own spot to attract app users) are included in Appendix 1.

Table 4. Section of the Table Describing the MVP of the xSpot Startup for Mobile Players

C		Mobile player		C		Mobile player		C		Mobile player	
C1		Dashboard		C2		Map		C3		Shop / Character Info	
User story		Komentarz		User story		Komentarz		User story		Comment	
C1.1	Registration	Register via email, Facebook, or Gmail.		C2.1	Power spot	Skill: power/strength – When a mobile player enters this spot, their avatar gains increased strength, making them more powerful in battles against other avatars. Strength can be gained by going to a spot and performing a specific task, e.g., lifting a barbell 10 times by tapping the screen (similar to San Andreas with the spacebar). The Web Player (spot owner) earns “coins” each time users enter their spot, which can be used to buy better spots and place them on the map (similar to Monopoly).		C3.1	Character Preview		
C1.2	Login			C2.2	Energy Spot	Skill: energy/food – When a mobile player enters this spot, their avatar gains energy needed to compete with another avatar, e.g., in a fighting game. To gain energy, the mobile player must complete a task like catching falling burgers within 5 seconds. The spot owner earns “coins.”		C3.2	Character Statistics Preview		
C1.3	Password Reset			C2.3	Super skill spot	Skill: super skill – When a mobile player enters this spot and completes a task like shooting a monster with a bow, they receive a “laser eyes” super skill that deals 30% damage to an enemy avatar in a fight. The Web Player earns coins each time a player defeats the monster. The person who placed the location cannot enter it themselves.		C3.3	Buy/Sell Acquired Items		
C1.4	Create AR Character			C2.4	Respect spot	Prestige – Visiting this location allows mobile players to earn skins like trendy clothes (t-shirts, hoodies, shoes), hairstyles, and jewelry to make their avatar stand out. These can be sold for coins. The spot owner also earns coins. The person who placed the location cannot enter it themselves.		C3.4			
C1.5				C2.5	One player fruits AR	AR game involving slicing falling fruits. The player gains dexterity, levels up, and earns virtual currency.		C3.5			
C1.6				C2.6	One player basketball AR	AR game where the avatar throws a basketball into a hoop. The player improves hand accuracy, levels up, and earns virtual currency.		C3.6			
C1.7				C2.7	One player football AR	AR game where the avatar kicks a ball at targets in the goal. The player improves foot accuracy and levels up.		C3.7			
C1.8				C2.8	Two players Boxing AR	AR fighting game between two players. Players can wager virtual currency; the winner takes all. There is a ranking and win record.		C3.8			
C1.9				C2.9	Two players Dancing AR	AR game similar to Guitar Hero. Players perform specific moves by pressing the correct buttons at the right time.		C3.9			
C1.10				C2.10	Two Players Volleyball AR	AR game where two users volley a ball over a net. They score points; the winner gets virtual money, ranks up, and levels up.		C3.10			

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

4. Validation of the xSpot Product MVP

In Chapter Four, which pertains to research methodology, the goal and subject of the research, research methods, as well as indicators, variables, techniques, and hypotheses will be explained.

Methodology refers to the knowledge of methods related to scientific research. It also involves considerations about the research subject, the process, and its outcomes. Undoubtedly, all fields of research encompass appropriate methods and techniques for conducting studies.

Research Objective

Scientific research is a process consisting of several compatible stages. Its purpose is to gain knowledge on a topic of interest to the researcher, and the result is a specific picture of reality (Sobol E, 1995, p. 854).

J. Pieter believes that scientific research has several meanings. Broadly speaking, it encompasses all activities undertaken to understand or verify a given phenomenon (1995, p. 104).

S. Nowak defines scientific research as a set of scientific activities or a part of the cognitive process that enables solving a problem and verifying a hypothesis. To conduct scientific research, one must define elements such as the problem, hypotheses, scope of the study, and its goal (2011, p. 272).

According to W. Dutkiewicz, the general aim of research is to understand a certain reality—to describe the subject, individual, phenomenon, or institution (2001, p. 50).

M. Łobocki expresses the view that the goal of research is the final outcome the researcher aims to achieve in the cognitive process using appropriate techniques and actions (Łobocki M, 1984, p. 58).

The goal of this research is to verify respondents' opinions regarding market demand for the xSpot startup product.

4.1. Research Problem

Properly defining problems and hypotheses allows for accurate scientific research. M. Łobocki defines research problems as specific questions that need to be answered during the research procedure (1984, p. 58). Meanwhile, W. Zaczyński defines a research problem as a person confronting a particular difficulty (Zaczyński, 1995, p. 30).

It is important that while formulating problems, the researcher meets the following criteria: the problem must present a specific relationship between variables, be clear, measurable (i.e., researchable), and formulated as a question (Łobocki M, 1984, p. 126). Properly formulated research problems must consider social needs, the researcher's interests, and knowledge of the relevant subject matter (Łobocki M, 1984, p. 126).

Based on the above, the main research problem of this thesis is:

- What role will augmented reality (AR) play in a technologically revolutionized economy?

In addition to the main problem, the following specific research questions were formulated:

- Do respondents find augmented reality attractive?
- How have respondents used augmented reality so far?
- What is the best use case for AR according to respondents?
- Do most AR users belong to Generation Z?
- Does the presence of AR in a company's marketing communication make it appear more attractive to respondents?
- How does AR marketing influence brand attractiveness and willingness to buy?

Formulating research problems enables the development of hypotheses necessary for obtaining valid scientific results. M. Łobocki states that the competence of a hypothesis is determined by whether it can be validated and whether it presents relationships between events, variables, and facts (2007, p. 136–138). According to W. Okoń, hypotheses are unverified statements that can be tested (1984, p. 97). W. Pytkowski believes a hypothesis is an assumption derived from the scope of the research and the researcher's knowledge (1981, p. 153).

Based on the main research problem and existing knowledge, the main hypothesis was formulated:

- The way AR technology is used in the xSpot startup has the potential to become key in marketing communication with Generation Z.

Additionally, the following auxiliary research hypotheses were proposed:

- Augmented reality technology will become increasingly popular among Generation Z representatives.
- The AR market will experience significant growth in the next decade.
- The approach proposed by xSpot is positively received by Generation Z as an innovative and non-intrusive form of marketing communication.

To verify these hypotheses, a study of the phenomenon had to be conducted using appropriate methods, tools, and techniques.

4.2. Variables and Indicators

Variables used in scientific research are extremely important; without them, it is impossible to conduct a proper research process or achieve satisfactory results. Variables are an attempt to specify the research problems in more detail (Łobocki M., 2007, p. 190). They are usually the basic symptoms, features, and characteristics of the phenomenon, fact, or process under study, or various types of factors that are their cause or effect. Each variable has different values (Łobocki M., 2007, p. 193). Currently, the literature on the subject includes various classifications of variables. Among them are binary and multivalued variables. An example of a binary variable is gender, while an example of a multivalued variable includes all other variables, such as education level: primary – secondary – higher (Brzeziński J., 1996, p. 184). M. Łobocki argues that independent variables are factors that determine changes in outcomes, while dependent variables are those influenced by independent variables (2007, p. 195).

In research, the most useful classification is based on the causes or effects associated with the variables. This includes primarily dependent and independent variables. Independent variables refer to various types of activities and influences. Independent variables can be summarized as actions intended to cause specific outcomes, while dependent variables are the real or assumed effects of the independent variables studied (Brzeziński J., 1996, p. 186). S. Nowak states that an indicator of a given phenomenon R can be defined as phenomenon N, whose observation allows one to determine whether R has occurred (2011, p. 292). He distinguishes three types of indicators:

- **Definitional** – derived from the definition of a fact or phenomenon;
- **Inferential** – referring to phenomena that are unobservable and concern invisible hypothetical variables;
- **Empirical** – related to the observation of a particular phenomenon.

All of the above indicators are fundamental conditions for properly organized quantitative research.

For this study, the following variables were formulated:

- Independent variables: age, gender

- Dependent variables: education level, place of residence

Indicators include: respondents' knowledge of new technologies, numerical data obtained during the research process.

4.3. Methods, Techniques, Tools

The proper identification of the researched phenomenon also depends on the appropriate choice of research techniques and methods. According to S. Nowak, research methods are all ways of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data to justify answers to previously posed research questions (2011, p. 22). To conduct proper research, it is essential to select the correct method. The choice depends on the research goal, the subject, and all materials gathered around the research topic (Zaczyński W., 1995, p. 19).

T. Plich defined a method as a set of activities that enable the researcher to explore the subject (1995, p. 66). He also outlined the conditions that must be met to select a research method. The first requirement is that it should be tailored to the problem; it should aid in completing the task, facilitate hypothesis formulation, and determine the course of action (1995, p. 68).

In this study, the diagnostic survey method was used, which allows the phenomenon to be fully and precisely described.

The primary function of a diagnostic survey is to collect information, while its distinguishing feature is probing the opinions of respondents participating in the study. This method is used in research involving surveys or interviews (Łobocki M., 2007, p. 140). This method is optimal because it helps formulate research problems, working hypotheses, and gather respondents' opinions on various elements important from the perspective of the research. The diagnostic survey method includes techniques such as interviews, conversations, and questionnaires (Dutkiewicz W., 2001, pp. 71–75).

According to Kamiński, research techniques are all possible methods of collecting materials necessary for conducting the research (1974, p. 54).

The technique used in this study was a questionnaire.

A questionnaire is a technique that allows for collecting information, usually from respondents who complete pre-prepared forms (Plich T., 1995, p. 141). The questions in the questionnaire must be specific and closely related to the research topic. Typically, these

include closed-ended questions (single or multiple choice) and open-ended questions (in which respondents express their own opinions on a given issue).

The questions in the questionnaire must address a specific matter, be formulated clearly and understandably, and include polite forms of address, e.g., “Have you ever used an augmented reality application?” (Łobocki M., 2007, p. 237).

In addition, the questionnaire should contain instructions for the respondents. This should include information such as the purpose of the study, details on anonymity, and a thank-you note for completing the form.

Example:

The purpose of the questionnaire is to conduct a study. It is intended for respondents of all genders, including students, workers, unemployed individuals, and residents of both urban and rural areas. It consists of three parts:

1. Introduction – General information about the questionnaire and its purpose.
2. Questions – These may be open- or closed-ended. Closed questions include predefined answers from which the respondent selects one that best represents their opinion. Open questions do not provide predefined answers, and respondents are asked to reply in their own words.
3. Demographics – The respondent provides age, gender, status, and education level.

Defining the territorial scope and research group is another key stage in the methodological preparation of research. The research area is not limited to a physical location but also includes the characteristics and issues that need to be examined (Plich T., 1995, p. 178). Zaczyński emphasizes that research methods and organization are always determined by research problems and hypotheses (1994, p. 153).

4.4. Product Evaluation of xSpot

Respondent Structure

The study involved 116 participants, of whom 37.9% were men and 62.1% were women.

Figure 25. Gender of respondents by percentage

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Figure 26 presents the percentage distribution of survey respondents, which decreases with age. The most represented group is Generation Z, i.e., those born after 1995, in age ranges such as: 20–24 years old (59%) and 15–19 years old (9%). The next most represented generation is Millennials – 25–29 years old (25%) and 30–34 years old (5%). 2% represent Generation X. It should be emphasized that generational boundaries are fluid and not rigid; often, a person’s generational affiliation is defined by the environment in which they reside.

Figure 26. Age of respondents by percentage

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The majority of respondents come from cities with more than 200,000 inhabitants, accounting for 50.9%. The second largest group comes from cities with up to 50,000 inhabitants, while the third group consists of people from rural areas.

Figure 27. Place of residence of respondents by percentage

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The largest group of respondents has higher education, accounting for 66.4% of the total, followed by those with secondary education at 31.8%.

Figure 28. Respondents' education by percentage

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Response Structure

The first question aimed to verify what percentage of the market is aware of, and how well they understand, what augmented reality is.

The majority of respondents (62.1%) have knowledge of what augmented reality is, while 37.9% confused the technology with virtual reality.

Czy wiesz, czym się charakteryzuje i wyróżnia "Rozszerzona Rzeczywistość" ?

116 odpowiedzi

Figure 29. Characteristics of Augmented Reality According to Respondents – Question 1

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The aim of the second question was to verify how often, and whether at all, respondents had practical experience with augmented reality.

As many as 56.9% of respondents frequently use filters in applications such as Snapchat and Messenger, while 35.3% have used such augmented reality solutions at least once. A small percentage, only 6.9%, have never used such a solution.

Czy zdarzyło Ci korzystać z "filtrów" w takich aplikacjach jak Snapchat / Messenger?

116 odpowiedzi

Figure 30. Use of Augmented Reality Filters on Snapchat and Messenger – Question 2

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The third question referred to general impressions when using augmented reality. When rating the entertainment value on a scale from 1 ("not fun at all") to 5 ("very fun"), 18.1% of respondents gave the highest rating of "5", 1.9% rated it "4", 26.7% chose "3", 14.7% selected "2", and 8.6% rated it "1". In practice, this means that users find AR to be a fairly fun form of communication with friends.

Czy uważasz, że korzystanie z filtrów na Snapchat lub Messenger jest zabawne / fajne / ciekawe?
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 31. Attractiveness of Snapchat and Messenger Filters – Question 3

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question four aimed to closely examine the assessment of users of mobile applications such as Snapchat, in which augmented reality is used.

The majority—59.5%—have not played AR games on the Snapchat app. This is likely due to the fact that after Instagram and Facebook introduced the "stories" functionality in their apps, some users left Snapchat. A smaller portion of respondents, 36.2%, have played such a game at least once, and 4.3% play regularly.

Czy zdarzyło Ci się grać w gry na Snapchatcie, które wykorzystywały filtry rozszerzające rzeczywistość?
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 32. Familiarity with AR games in the Snapchat app – Question 4

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question five specifically concerned the attractiveness of AR games in the Snapchat app, aiming to assess how appealing they are and whether they could serve as a benchmark for the xSpot startup.

The respondents who had played these games—39.4% of the total—rated them on a scale from 1 (Poor) to 5 (Very Attractive) as follows: the highest percentage, 45.7%, gave a rating of 3; 21.7% rated the games a 1; and the third most common rating was 4, with 17.4% of the votes.

Jeśli grałeś w grę mobilną na Snapchat, jak oceniasz jej atrakcyjność? Pomiń jeśli nie grałeś.
46 odpowiedzi

Figure 33. Attractiveness rating of AR games in the Snapchat app – question 5

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question six was directed at users of the Messenger app who had played games using augmented reality, in order to verify their popularity.

The majority, 54.3% of users, have never played a game based on augmented reality filters. However, 43.1% have played such a game once or twice, and 2.6% played more than that.

Czy zdarzyło Ci się grać w gry na Messengerze podczas rozmowy ze znajomym, które wykorzystywały filtry rozszerzające rzeczywistość?

116 odpowiedzi

Figure 34. Familiarity with AR games in the Messenger app – question 6

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question seven concerned the attractiveness of games using AR technology in the Messenger app, with the aim of determining a benchmark for the xSpot startup.

Users who had played AR games in the Messenger app accounted for 46.5% of all respondents. The majority of these users, 42.6%, rated the game's attractiveness as 3, 22.2% rated it as 4, and 18.5% as 2.

Jeśli grałeś w grę mobilną wykorzystującą rozszerzoną rzeczywistość na Messenger, jak oceniasz jej atrakcyjność? Pomiń jeśli nie grałeś.

54 odpowiedzi

Figure 35. Evaluation of the attractiveness of AR games in the Messenger app – question 7

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The next question concerned the general awareness of the game Pokémon GO among respondents, which serves as an inspiration for the xSpot game.

The majority, as many as 57.8% of people, do not know the game at all. However, 36.2% declare that they have played the game at least once in their life, and 6% play it frequently.

Czy zdarzyło Ci się grać w grę Pokemon Go?

116 odpowiedzi

Figure 36. Awareness of the game Pokémon GO – question 8

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 9 directly addressed the assessment of the attractiveness of the game Pokémon GO on a scale from 1 (Poor) to 5 (Very attractive)

A total of 44.8% of all respondents have played Pokémon GO. Among this group, as many as 32.7% rated the game a 4, while 23.1% rated it a 5. Conversely, an equal 23.1% gave it a score of 2. In practice, this means that those who have played or still play Pokémon GO

have become highly engaged in the game, and it represents an optimal form of entertainment for them.

Jeśli grałeś w grę mobilną Pokemon Go, jak oceniasz jej atrakcyjność? Pomiń jeśli nie grałeś.
52 odpowiedzi

Figure 37. Attractiveness rating of Pokémon GO – question 9

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The purpose of the question was to summarize the general attitude of respondents toward applications using augmented reality, because after the earlier questions, those who initially confused augmented reality with virtual reality realized that they actually use this technology on a daily basis.

As many as 41.4% of respondents rated AR at 4, followed by 29% who gave it a 3, and 17.2% rated it a 5. Respondents clearly state that augmented reality is an attractive form of communication and holds significant development potential.

Jak oceniasz atrakcyjność samej technologii rozszerzonej rzeczywistości? Biorąc pod uwagę, takie aplikacje, jak: Messenger, Snapchat, PokemonGo
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 38. Assessment of the attractiveness of augmented reality technology based on applications like Messenger, Snapchat, and Pokémon GO – question 10

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

In question 11, examples of the use of augmented reality in marketing communication were presented. Its purpose was to assess respondents' attitudes toward this form of communication.

The majority, 73.3% of all respondents, gave a rating of 5, which means “Very attractive,” and slightly fewer, 18.1%, rated the communication as 4.

In practice, these responses reflect a positive attitude toward the possibilities that AR offers.

Marka Gucci umożliwia użytkownikom swojej aplikacji na wirtualne przymierzanie ciuchów w rozszerzonej rzeczywistości, z kolei aplikacja IKEA.... Jak oceniasz taką formę komunikacji z klientami?
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 39. Product visualization using augmented reality – question 11

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 12 relates directly to the consumption of visualized products. Its purpose was to validate the use of AR for visualizing a product in the context of a potential customer’s purchase decision.

The majority of respondents, 66.4%, gave a rating of 5, meaning “Yes, very much” on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means “No.” Another 22.4% rated the impact of AR on the purchase decision at level 4. Respondents collectively indicate that marketing communication through AR increases the desire to purchase a product among potential consumers.

Nawiązując do poprzedniego pytania, czy możliwość wizualizacji produktu zwiększa według ciebie chęć jego zakupu?

116 odpowiedzi

Figure 40. The impact of AR product visualization on purchase decisions – question 12

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The purpose of question 13 was to gather information about which form of using AR technology is considered the most valuable by respondents.

The majority, 79.3%, indicated "informational" use of the technology. In second place, with 67.2%, was the "educational" form, followed by "marketing communication" with 57.8%, and finally "entertainment" with 39.7% of the votes.

Jak sądzisz jakie formy wykorzystania rozszerzonej rzeczywistości są najtrafniejsze? (możesz zaznaczyć kilka odpowiedzi)

116 odpowiedzi

Figure 41. The most appropriate use of augmented reality – question 13

Źródło: (Opracowanie własne, 2020)

Question 14 aimed to verify the most attractive elements of AR technology from a market perspective.

The majority of respondents, 62.1%, indicated "The use of the real environment for gameplay / education / or informational purposes" as the most appealing.

In second place was "The combination of the virtual and real world" with 51.7%, and in third, "The ability to embed virtual characters/objects into the real world" with 40.5%.

Respondents suggest that the most interesting aspect of AR is using the surrounding environment for communication purposes. This is an excellent channel because it supports engagement and identification with the message, thanks to the fact that virtual information can "appear" around individual users whose surroundings differ from those of their friends.

Figure 42. The most attractive element of augmented reality – question 14

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 15 aimed to verify what portion of the market has their own Facebook avatar or Bitmoji.

The majority, 63.8% of respondents, stated that they have their own avatar, while 36.2% said they do not.

Czy posiadasz własne Bitmoji / Facebook avatar obrazujący twoją osobę?
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 43. Possession of Bitmoji / Facebook avatar – question 15

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The aim of Question 16 was to determine how strongly users identify with their avatar—that is, the virtual version of themselves.

Among the respondents who have an avatar (67.2% of all respondents), 59% stated that they identify with their avatar, while 41% said they do not identify with it at all. This result indicates that players value having their own avatar—a virtual and personalized representation of themselves in an individual way.

Czy utożsamiasz się ze stworzonym przez siebie avatar? (Pomiń jeśli nie masz avatara)
78 odpowiedzi

Figure 44. Identification with the user’s virtual version – Question 16

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 17 concerned users’ creative approach to the characters they create in mobile applications.

The largest group of respondents—30.4%—chose a rating of 3. In second place, ratings of 4 and 2 each received 26.6%. This indicates that some users use their avatar to express their individual style and to stand out in the online environment.

Czy uważasz, że avatar daje ci możliwość kreatywnego przedstawienia twojej osoby? (Pomiń jeśli nie masz avatara)
79 odpowiedzi

Figure 45. Avatar as a creative representation of the user – Question 17

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 18 focused on whether users pay attention to how their avatar looks and whether they can change its appearance.

This information is very important from the perspective of the xSpot product, whose entire gameplay revolves around the avatar and its individual appearance.

Opinions on this issue are quite divided. On a scale from 1 to 5, the largest portion—25.6% of respondents—indicated a score of 2, followed by 23.1% choosing 1, 20.5% voting 3, 16.7% rating it as very important with a score of 5, and finally, 14.1% chose 4. Overall, it can be said that the majority of users—51.3% who selected scores from 3 to 5—consider the ability to modify appearance to be important. This is not surprising, as in the previous question, a significant portion indicated they identify with their avatar— and one cannot identify with something to which they feel no connection.

Figure 46. Importance of avatar appearance customization – Question 18
Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The purpose of Question 19 was to identify what is currently missing in existing applications using AR technology. This was an especially important point, as it indicated market gaps that could potentially be filled by the xSpot product.

The largest number of users—38.8%—pointed to “The ability to play using a self-created avatar.” Next, 33.7% voted for “The ability to develop the avatar’s ‘home,’ like in The Sims,” and 30.6% indicated “The ability to develop the avatar’s skills, e.g., like in GTA.” These findings are very important for the xSpot product, as the game is designed to focus on using one’s avatar to play with friends, develop a personal growth space—such as a gym to boost strength and fitness, a changing room to customize clothes and appearance, and a kitchen to restore energy and health. The last point, about avatar skill development, aligns with xSpot’s concept in which players can improve their character “locally” (e.g., at home), but real progress comes from leaving the house and visiting specific “Spots,” where rewards await to boost the avatar’s attributes in various areas.

Figure 47. What is lacking in mobile AR games – Question 19

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

After presenting the AR technology, competitive solutions, and the product concept of the xSpot startup—which was described in the survey as follows: "Let's assume there is a game—let's call it xSpot—in augmented reality (like in the GIF), where there is an avatar created by you, and you can, for example, play tennis or box with a friend in multiplayer mode." Alongside this, a GIF was shown to illustrate the concept, with a screenshot presented in Figure 25. Respondents were then asked to assess the attractiveness of this concept in their eyes.

Figure 48. AR Game Snapchat

Source: (Snapchat, 2020)

On a scale from 1 (rather uninteresting) to 5 (very interesting), the highest number of respondents—31%—chose a rating of 4. The second most common rating was 3 with 27.6%, followed by rating 5 with 18.1%.

Assuming that respondents who answered 4 or 5 would be interested in the game—since they did not respond with a firm 1, 2, or a neutral 3—49.1% of respondents would be inclined to play xSpot. Whether they would stay depends on how engaging the gameplay is; however, in my opinion, this is a very good result that indicates the potential of the xSpot game.

Czy uważasz, że gra xSpot mogłaby być dla Ciebie ciekawą formą rozrywki i spędzenia czasu wolnego, ze znajomymi?
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 49. Evaluation of the xSpot mobile app concept – Question 20

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The next question focused on validating the design assumptions for the xSpot MVP — specifically, whether the planned features have user support and identifying the most attractive gameplay formats, according to respondents, in which AR technology would be interesting to use.

The highest number of respondents, 44%, indicated "Playing tennis", which shows that elements of action, competition, and sports in a mobile game are very important. This was also given special attention in the xSpot MVP assumptions, as it is a core functionality designed to quickly engage the largest number of users. In second place, with 35.3%, was "Furnishing my avatar's 'living space'". Users emphasized that the feeling of needing to care for one's avatar—so that it "feels good"—is crucial for mobile gamers. A similar concept was successful in Tamagotchi, a game from the early 2000s. Aware of this, the development roadmap includes not only modifying the avatar's appearance but also allowing the customization and personalization of its "living space". This is not a core entertainment feature and will therefore be introduced in a future version of the product.

The third most selected functionality was "Designing clothes for my avatar", with 33.6%. This point ties back to the entire concept of self-expression online, allowing players to show off their artistic and creative side. However, as this is not an essential feature likely to attract users in the first version, it has been postponed to later development stages.

Figure 50. The most interesting forms of gameplay using AR – Question 21

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

The goal of Question 22 was to verify whether the game xSpot alone is capable of attracting users who want to personalize or improve their avatar by visiting locations that wish to promote themselves.

Respondents emphasized the attractiveness of the item offered at a given location — as many as 54.1% answered "yes," but it depends on what the location offers for their avatar and how appealing it is. Additionally, 9.9% said they would visit a spot specifically to collect a unique item. Together, this amounts to 64% of respondents interested in this form of entertainment, which, in my opinion, is a very positive result. On the other hand, 36% answered that they would not visit a location with a unique product, regardless of how attractive or unique it would be for their avatar.

Jeśli dowolny sklep zaproponowałby możliwość uzyskania np. unikatowej koszulki lub mocy dla twojego awatara w swojej lokalizacji, to udałbyś w to miejsce, aby uzyskać nagrodę?

111 odpowiedzi

Figure 51. Attracting customers using the xSpot application – Question 22

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 23 aimed to examine the attractiveness of promotions offered through the xSpot mobile game. With a clear target user base, introducing promotions related to purchases at specific venues is an excellent form of sales promotion because it directly targets potential customers. The results are as follows:

- 39.3% of respondents said yes, they would find this form of promotion attractive, but it would depend on the appeal of the item offered by the venue. In practice, this means that beyond offering a discount on products at a location, attention must also be paid to the attractiveness of the benefits offered to the avatar of the potential customer.
- 25% considered this sales promotion form attractive regardless of whether the virtual benefit was interesting or not — for this group, the discount on the product itself was the most important factor.
- 35.7% responded that this type of promotion was not attractive at all.

The results indicate that players with avatars — who would already be visiting various places to develop their characters — would be open to participating in sales promotions offered by those locations. This is very positive news, as it confirms the product and market assumptions of the xSpot startup.

Czy uznałabyś to za atrakcyjne, jeśli dowolna restauracja zaproponowałaby możliwość uzyskania dodatkowej energii i mocy dla twojego awatara za p...e do jej lokalu jednocześnie oferując zniżkę 15%?
112 odpowiedzi

Figure 52. Sales promotion using xSpot – Question 23

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

Question 24, the final one, concerned respondents' general attitude toward marketing communication through the xSpot channel. Just like the Gucci brand, which allowed users to virtually try on its clothes, xSpot also offers players interaction with brands and their products — but in a virtual version. The products are visualized in augmented reality (AR), with the use of avatars. However, this does not preclude the future implementation of a feature allowing users to try on avatar clothing themselves, similar to the Gucci app. Respondents answered as follows:

- 37.9% said "yes," but it depends on the attractiveness of the item,
- 22.4% responded positively regardless of the value of the benefit offered,
- while 39.7% voted "no," indicating that this form of communication wouldn't make a difference to them.

In summary, a positive attitude was demonstrated by 60.3%, who believe that this form of marketing communication would change their perception of a brand, making it seem more modern and attractive

Czy uważasz, że marka, która proponowałaby wirtualny benefit dla twojego awatara np. unikatową koszulkę ze swoim logo w grze xSpot byłaby atrakcyjniejsza od innych przez innowacyjne podejście?
116 odpowiedzi

Figure 53. Marketing communication using the xSpot channel – Question 24

Source: (Own elaboration, 2020)

CONCLUSION

Augmented Reality (AR) has the potential to become a key form of marketing communication in the future. Case studies show that attempts to use it for such purposes are continually being made. Moreover, the market is still in its early stages, with significant growth potential, meaning that currently, there are low entry barriers in terms of competition, but high technical requirements for creating a product based on this technology.

Young Internet users, particularly those from Generation Z, represent the largest group likely to benefit the most from AR due to their adaptation to new technologies and preference for fast, image- or video-based communication. They seek non-traditional ways to communicate with brands while expressing their individualism and creativity.

This thesis focused on the xSpot startup, which combines elements such as: the virtual and real world, consumers and businesses, and players with their friends. The mission of the product is to create a space for AR technology, which is currently scattered across many platforms, apps, and environments. The overarching goal is to provide a place where Gen Z users can creatively express their unique style, interact with friends in direct competition (like on a virtual boxing ring), or through gamified challenges (such as “who visited more places and collected more unique items for their avatar”).

For businesses, it should be a platform to present their brand’s uniqueness in a physical location displayed on the game's mobile map, or through an offered benefit (e.g., a branded virtual item), which could become the most desired item within the xSpot community. In addition to marketing communication — the most engaging form in today’s market — xSpot also provides an ideal channel for promoting sales. In xSpot, marketing and sales promotion create a synergistic effect of mutually reinforcing elements.

This study positively validated the hypothesis that **xSpot’s use of AR technology has the potential to become a key tool in marketing communication with Generation Z.** Throughout the thesis, 49% of respondents responded positively to the value proposition presented by xSpot.

Furthermore, the assumptions regarding MVP functionality were also confirmed, as they were based on avatar creation and sports competition with other users. The largest group — 38.8% of respondents — indicated that what is currently missing in AR apps is the ability to play as a self-created avatar, and 44% pointed to playing tennis with a friend as the most interesting AR entertainment format. The communication form using xSpot was also

positively received — 64% of respondents would visit a location offering a virtual benefit for their avatar, provided it was attractive enough.

In summary, the research results indicate that the development and growth potential of the xSpot startup is aligned with its initial assumptions.

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Marker-based AR.....	6
Figure 2. Markerless AR.....	7
Figure 3. Location-based Augmented Reality.....	7
Figure 4. Number of Augmented Reality Users in the U.S.....	9
Figure 5. Global number of mobile devices supporting 5G from 2021 to 2025 (in billions).....	10
Figure 6. The importance of 5G for mobile applications.....	11
Figure 7. “Burn That Ad” Augmented Reality Campaign by Burger King.....	13
Figure 8. Gucci Mobile App Using Augmented Reality.....	14
Figure 9. IKEA App in Augmented Reality.....	15
Figure 10. E-Commerce App in Augmented Reality as Part of Adidas Marketing Campaign.....	16
Figure 11. Philadelphia Phillies Web App in Augmented Reality.....	17
Figure 12. LEGO Augmented Reality App.....	17
Figure 13. Web App in Augmented Reality by Philadelphia Phillies.....	18
Figure 14. Generation Z Online.....	20
Figure 15. Decline in Generation Z’s Presence on Facebook.....	21
Figure 16. Growth in Generation Z’s Presence on Instagram.....	21
Figure 17. Startup Curve.....	27
Figure 18. Startup Development Stages.....	28
Figure 19. Design Thinking Process.....	32
Figure 20. Empathy Map.....	33
Figure 21. Example Application of the 5 Why Method.....	35
Figure 22. Business Model Canvas.....	40
Figure 23. Target Audience Model.....	41
Figure 24. Lean Startup Development Diagram.....	47
Figure 25. Gender of respondents by percentage.....	55
Figure 26. Age of respondents by percentage.....	56
Figure 27. Place of residence of respondents by percentage.....	56
Figure 28. Respondents’ education by percentage.....	56
Figure 29. Characteristics of Augmented Reality According to Respondents – Question 1.....	57
Figure 30. Use of Augmented Reality Filters on Snapchat and Messenger – Question 2.....	57
Figure 31. Attractiveness of Snapchat and Messenger Filters – Question 3.....	58
Figure 32. Familiarity with AR games in the Snapchat app – Question 4.....	58
Figure 33. Attractiveness rating of AR games in the Snapchat app – question 5.....	59
Figure 34. Familiarity with AR games in the Messenger app – question 6.....	59
Figure 35. Evaluation of the attractiveness of AR games in the Messenger app – question 7.....	60

Figure 36. Awareness of the game Pokémon GO – question 8.....	60
Figure 37. Attractiveness rating of Pokémon GO – question 9.....	61
Figure 38. Assessment of the attractiveness of augmented reality technology based on applications like Messenger, Snapchat, and Pokémon GO – question 10.....	61
Figure 39. Product visualization using augmented reality – question 11.....	62
Figure 40. The impact of AR product visualization on purchase decisions – question 12.....	63
Figure 41. The most appropriate use of augmented reality – question 13.....	63
Figure 42. The most attractive element of augmented reality – question 14.....	64
Figure 43. Possession of Bitmoji / Facebook avatar – question 15.....	64
Figure 44. Identification with the user’s virtual version – Question 16.....	65
Figure 45. Avatar as a creative representation of the user – Question 17.....	65
Figure 46. Importance of avatar appearance customization – Question 18.....	66
Figure 47. What is lacking in mobile AR games – Question 19.....	67
Figure 48. AR Game Snapchat.....	67
Figure 49. Evaluation of the xSpot mobile app concept – Question 20.....	68
Figure 50. The most interesting forms of gameplay using AR – Question 21.....	69
Figure 51. Attracting customers using the xSpot application – Question 22.....	70
Figure 52. Sales promotion using xSpot – Question 23.....	71
Figure 53. Marketing communication using the xSpot channel – Question 24.....	72

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Differences Between Consumer Generations.....	23
Table 2. Guiding Questions in the 6 Thinking Hats Method.....	36
Table 3. Business Model Canvas for xSpot Startup.....	45
Table 4. Section of the Table Describing the MVP of the xSpot Startup for Mobile Players.....	49

APPENDIX LIST

1. Appendix 1 – xSpot – MVP

A		Global Admin		A		Global Admin / Web App User		A		Global Admin	
A1		Dashboard		A2		Map		A3		Settings	
User story		Comment / Clarification		User story		Comment / Clarification		User story		Comment / Clarification	
A1.1	User Statistics	As a super admin, I want to view the number of registered users daily, weekly, monthly, and in total, as well as the number currently online, with filters by country.		A2.1	Map Management	Manage Default Spots As a super admin, I want to add/edit/delete default spots for web players to place on the map. Categories: Skills: power, energy, super skill, respect Games: one-player and two-player games		A3.1	Managing Super Admins	As a super admin, I want to be able to add, remove, and edit other admins – (CRUD – create, read, update, and delete).	
A1.2	Spot Statistics	I want to know how many spots (locations) were created on a given day/week/month and overall.		A2.2	Power spot	Power Spot: Avatars gain strength via tasks (e.g., lifting weights). Web players earn AS coins from visits		A3.2			
A1.3	Login	Standard login functionality.		A2.3	Energy spot	Energy Spot: Replenish avatar energy (e.g., catching falling burgers in time). Spot owners earn AS coins.		A3.3			
A1.4				A2.4	Super skill spot	Super Skill Spot: Completing challenges (e.g., defeating a monster) gives powerful skills (e.g., laser eyes).		A3.4			

A1.5			A2.5	Respect spot	Respect Spot: Collect cosmetic avatar items (clothes, accessories). Owners earn AS coins from visits.	A3.5				
A1.6			A2.6	One player fruits AR	One-player AR: Fruit Ninja-style, Basketball shootout, Football penalty shots.	A3.6				
A1.7			A2.7	One player basketball AR	One Player Basketball AR – An AR game where the player uses their avatar to shoot a basketball into a hoop → the player improves hand accuracy → they can reach higher levels and earn virtual currency.	A3.7				
A1.8			A2.8	One player football AR	One Player Football AR – An AR game where the player shoots a ball into designated goal areas → the player improves foot accuracy → they can reach higher levels.	A3.8				
A1.9			A2.9	Two players Boxing AR	Two Players Boxing AR – An AR game between two players involving a fistfight → players can bet virtual currency → the winner takes all, and there's also a ranking and win tracking system.	A3.9				
A1.10			A2.10	Two players Dancing AR	Two Players Dancing AR – An AR game similar to Guitar Hero that involves performing specific moves by clicking the correct buttons at the right time.	A3.10				
A1.11			A2.11	Two Players Volleyball AR	Two Players Volleyball AR – An AR game where two users have a net in the middle and hit the ball over it → they score points, and the winner of the match wins virtual money; a ranking is created and levels are earned.	A3.11				
B	Web player			B	Web player			B	Web player	
B1	Dashboard			B2				B3		
User story		Comment / Clarification		User story			Comment	User story		Comment / Clarification
B1.1	Registration			B2.1	Placing spots			B3.1		
B1.2	Login			B2.2	Statistics of my spots			B3.2		
B1.3	Character preview		As a player, I want to see my character and their equipment.	B2.3				B3.3		
B1.4				B2.4				B3.4		
C	Mobile player		C	Mobile player			C	Mobile player		
C1	Dashboard		C2	Mapa			C3	Sklep /		

User story		Comment / Clarification	User story		Comment / Clarification	User story		Comment / Clarification
C1.1	Registration	Email, Facebook, Gmail	C2.1	Power spot	a) Power/Strength – If a mobile player enters this spot, their avatar gains increased strength, making them more powerful in a battle against another avatar. Strength can be gained by going to the spot and completing a specific task with the avatar, for example, lifting a barbell 10 times by tapping the screen (like using the spacebar in GTA: San Andreas). Meanwhile, the web player who owns the spot earns "AS coins" for each user entry, which they can use to buy and place better spots on the map (similar to Monopoly).	C3.1	Character preview	
C1.2	Login		C2.2	Energy spot	b) Energy/Food – If a mobile player enters this spot, their avatar gains the energy needed to compete with another avatar, e.g., in a fighting game. To gain energy, the mobile player must complete a task such as catching a certain number of falling burgers within 5 seconds. The spot owner receives "AS coins."	C3.2	Character stats preview	
C1.3	Password reset		C2.3	Super skill spot	c) Super Skill – If the mobile player visits this location and completes a specific task, e.g., killing a monster with a bow, they unlock a super skill like "laser eyes," which reduces the opponent's health by 30% in a fighting game. The web player who placed this spot earns AS coins for every player who defeats the monster. ***The player who placed the location cannot access it themselves.	C3.3	Ability to buy/sell obtained items	
C1.4	Creating AR character		C2.4	Respect spot	d) Prestige – By visiting this location, the mobile player can collect avatar "skins," such as trendy t-shirts, hoodies, shoes, hairstyles, or jewelry that help them stand out. These items can also be sold for AS coins. The player who placed the spot also receives AS coins. ***The player who placed this location cannot access it themselves.	C3.4		
C1.5			C2.5	One Player Fruits AR	One Player Fruits AR – An AR game involving slicing fruits falling from above. The player increases their dexterity, levels up in the game, and earns virtual currency.	C3.5		
C1.6			C2.6	One Player Basketball AR	One Player Basketball AR – An AR game in which the player throws a ball into a basket using their avatar. The player improves their hand accuracy, gains higher levels, and earns virtual currency.	C3.6		
C1.7			C2.7	One player football AR	One Player Football AR – An AR game in which the player shoots a ball into designated goal areas. The player improves foot accuracy and progresses through levels.	C3.7		
C1.8			C2.8	Two players	Two Players Boxing AR – An AR fighting game between two players. Players can bet virtual currency, and	C3.8		

				Boxing AR	the winner takes it all. A ranking system and win count are included.			
C1.9			C2.9	Two players Dancing AR	Two Players Dancing AR – An AR game similar to Guitar Hero, where players must perform the correct moves by clicking corresponding buttons at the right time.	C3.9		
C1.10			C2.10	Two Players Volleyball AR	An AR game where two users play volleyball over a net. Players score points, and the winner earns virtual currency. A ranking system and level progression are included.	C3.10		